

Data-Driven Forward Prediction for Acoustic Metamaterial Topology Optimization

Sourava Prasad Mishra, Paweł Kudela

Institute of Fluid-Flow Machinery, Polish Academy of Sciences, Fiszerza 14, 80-231 Gdańsk, Poland

Background, Motivation and Objective

Metamaterials are architected structures with exotic physical properties such as selective blocking of ultrasonic waves. Due to such property metamaterials have found significant usage in ultrasonic imaging and microbubble-based contrast-enhanced ultrasound. One example application of metamaterial is to block fundamental waves while allowing harmonic waves to pass through, aiding in artifact free imaging. Properties emerge from the geometry and arrangement of the constituents of the unit cells in metamaterials. Identifying optimal configurations for specific responses remains a computational challenge. In this work, we propose a data-driven topology optimization framework designed to predict the dispersion vector. Using machine learning techniques, our method accelerates the forward prediction process compared to traditional numerical solvers. We benchmark the proposed algorithm against established methodologies, demonstrating superior performance in terms of computational efficiency and comparable predictive accuracy for complex acoustic bandgap structures.

Statement of Contribution/Methods

We represent metamaterial topologies as binary images with solid material and void regions. The image is used as inputs to our model designed to predict the full dispersion vector. The dispersion vector is used to describe the relationship between frequency and reduced wavevector in a material. We use a Vision Transformer (ViT) architecture, leveraging self-attention mechanisms to model topology images. Unlike traditional approaches, our approach enables the capture of both local details and global geometric symmetries to achieves superior accuracy in predicting metamaterial properties.

Results/Discussion

We split a dataset of topology images and dispersion vector into train and test sets and report the results of our model on the test set. Our benchmarking results confirm the model's robustness and usability across diverse metamaterial configurations. Furthermore, the proposed method offers significant computational efficiency and enables the rapid evaluation of thousands of candidate designs in seconds.

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